

Interaction of phenylarsonic acid derivatives with Group IIA metal ions

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The proton-ligand stability constants and stability constants of complexes of Group IIA metal ions with *o*-amino- and *o*-hydroxyphenylarsonic acids have been determined potentiometrically at 30° at ionic strengths of 0.05, 0.10, 0.20 *M* and also at 20° and 40° at an ionic strength of 0.05 *M*. The stability order for 1 : 1 complexes is Ca^{II} < Sr^{II} < Ba^{II}. In case of Mg^{II} and Be^{II} complexes, precipitation occurred early during titration. The thermodynamic parameters have been evaluated.

The complexes of some of the transition metal ions with phenylarsonic acid have been studied¹. In the present work, the proton-ligand stability constants of *o*-amino- and *o*-hydroxyphenylarsonic acids with Group IIA metal ions have been determined at 30° in aqueous solution and at various ionic strengths ($\mu = 0.05, 0.10, 0.20 M$). These constants have been also determined at 20 and 40° at an ionic strength of 0.05 *M*. The Bjerrum-Calvin pH-titration technique² as adopted by Irving and Rossotti³ was employed for the study. The thermodynamic stability constants have also been evaluated at 30° by extrapolation to zero ionic strength. The study could not be reported for Mg^{II} and Be^{II} due to precipitation during titrations.

Results and discussion

The ligands, *o*-amino- and *o*-hydroxyphenylarsonic acids contain amino and hydroxy groups, respectively, in addition to arsonic acid group. The amino group is protonated in the solution, so both the ligands release three protons,

where, X = C₆H₅-AsO₃

The ligand [X-NH₂]²⁻ can coordinate through amino-nitrogen and oxygen of arsonate group (AsO₃), and [X-O]³⁻ can coordinate through phenoxy as well as arsonate (AsO₃) oxygens. So these ligands can form chelates with metal ion, which are expected to be highly stable. The proton-ligand stability constants (Table 1) for *o*-hydroxyphenylarsonic acid are higher than those of *o*-aminophenylarsonic acid at all temperatures and ionic strengths. The values record a decrease with rise of temperature and increase of ionic strength.

The values of stability constants (log *K*) of the metal complexes (Table 2) are in the order, Ca^{II} < Sr^{II} < Ba^{II}, which is in accordance with values of radii of hydrated cations. Moreover, the observed order is due to the nature of the ligands which contain arsonate group (AsO₃) in addition to amino and hydroxy group in the *ortho*-position. The same order has been found in the case of anions of oxygenated inorganic acids of large dimensions^{3,4}. The stability order regarding the nature of ligands is *o*-aminophenylarsonic acid > *o*-hydroxyphenylarsonic, indicating the preference of M²⁺ ions for (N,O) over (O,O) coordination. The values of the thermodynamic stability constant, free energy change (ΔG), enthalpy change (ΔH) and en-

Table 1. Proton-ligand constants of *o*-amino- and *o*-hydroxyphenylarsonic acids in aqueous solution

Temp. °C	μ <i>M</i>	<i>o</i> -Aminophenylarsonic acid			<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenylarsonic acid		
		log K_1^H	log K_2^H	log K_3^H	log K_1^H	log K_2^H	log K_3^H
20	0.05	12.20	10.30	4.00	13.00	11.20	9.91
30	0.05	11.45	9.90	3.70	12.60	11.00	9.80
	0.10	10.65	9.55	3.65	12.36	10.90	9.40
	0.20	10.40	9.40	3.50	12.00	10.60	9.35
40	0.05	10.60	9.60	3.67	11.30	10.70	9.62

Table 2. Stability constants and thermodynamic functions for metal complexes of phenylarsonic acid derivatives

Metal ion	Temp °C	μ <i>M</i>	<i>o</i> -Aminophenylarsonic acid			<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenylarsonic acid				
			$\log K$	$-\Delta G$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta H$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S$ cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	$\log K$	$-\Delta G$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta H$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S$ cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
Ca ^{II}	20	0.05	8.40	11.22		113.41	7.35	9.82		73.68
	30	0.00	6.40	8.84			8.40	11.60		
		0.05	5.27	7.28	44.45	117.52	6.27	8.66	31.41	75.08
		0.10	4.50	6.21			5.48	7.57		
	40	0.20	4.35	6.01			4.34	5.99		
Sr ^{II}	20	0.05	4.30	6.13		122.24	5.30	7.56		76.19
	30	0.05	8.99	12.01		48.77	7.92	10.58		83.17
		0.00	9.80	13.54			9.30	12.84		
		0.05	7.92	10.94	26.30	50.69	7.21	9.96	34.95	82.47
	40	0.20	5.18	7.15			6.23	8.60		
Ba ^{II}	20	0.05	7.30	10.41		50.76	5.65	8.06		85.91
	30	0.05	11.67	15.59		151.02	8.38	11.19		75.52
		0.00	11.50	15.88			10.55	14.57		
		0.05	9.31	12.86	59.84	155.04	7.81	10.79	33.32	74.35
	40	0.20	6.70	9.25			6.60	9.11		
	0.05	6.53	9.02			5.22	7.21			
	0.05	8.00	11.41		154.72	6.39	9.12		77.31	

tropy change (ΔS) associated with the complexes formation are given in Table 2. The negative values of ΔG in case of all the complexes suggest the spontaneous formation of the complexes of high stability. Both ΔH and ΔS are negative. So the enthalpy change is favorable while the entropy term is unfavorable for the formation of these complexes. This can be due to the substitution of the solvent molecules attached to the metal ion by the ligands resulting in the release of solvent molecules.

Experimental

o-Aminophenylarsonic acid was prepared by the reduction of *o*-nitrophenylarsonic acid and purified (m.p. 153°). *o*-Hydroxyphenylarsonic acid was prepared by adding Na₂AsO₃ to diazonium salt of *o*-aminophenol and the resulting mixture was heated and acidified to get the product, m.p. 196°. The solutions (0.05 *M*) of the *o*-amino- and *o*-hydroxyphenylarsonic acids were prepared in double-distilled water for potentiometric studies.

A Systronic 33 pH meter with a glass and calomel electrode assembly was used. The titrations were carried at 20, 30 and 40 ± 0.1° in a constant temperature water-bath. The mole ratio of metal-to-ligand was kept at 1 : 5 in order to fulfil the maximum coordination number of the metal. The following solutions (total initial volume 20 ml) were titrated against a standard alkali: (A) 2 ml of HClO₄ (0.05 *M*); (B) A + 2 ml of ligand (0.05 *M*); (C) B + 2 ml of metal ion (0.01 *M*). The ionic strength (0.05, 0.10 and 0.20 *M*) was maintained by adding calculated amount of sodium perchlorate solution. Stability constants were calculated according to the procedure of Irving and Rossotti³.

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